

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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EPIDEMIOLOGY OF HUMAN MYCOTIC KERATITIS IN TANTA UNIVERSITY OPHTHALMOLOGY HOSPITAL**ABSTRACT:**

The target of the present study was to evaluate the spreading mycotic infection of human corneal ulcers on the basis of the predisposing factors. Contact lens users and farmers were found to be more susceptible for mycotic keratitis; also immunocompromised male patients aged more than 40 years with rural residence were the most frequent inhabitants of fungal corneal ulcers, during summer, and spring seasons. *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus niger* were the most common species, isolated from the studied mycotic keratitis cases, mostly causing central corneal lesions in right more than left eyes. On the other hand, out of 595 cases of different types of corneal ulcers, fungi were isolated from 50 cases.

KEY WORDS:

Epidemiology, fungal keratitis, fungal corneal infections, risk factors, causal fungi of corneal ulcers

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INTRODUCTION:

Mycotic keratitis is a disease caused by fungal invasion into the corneal stroma. It is an exogenous infection, attacking the injured corneal epithelium, and establishes the fungal growth within the collagen bound lamellae of stromal layer of cornea. Mycotic keratitis is considered to be a resistant corneal ulcer, which possesses aggressive microbial growth, and becomes not responding to conventional treatments for at least one week, or more, and even becomes worse due to continued fungal growth, and toxification of cornea by drugs, and fungal secretions (Tanure *et al.*, 2000).

The severity of corneal fungal infections depends on the complete destruction of loosen stromal layer by the proliferation of large-sized hyphae of filamentous fungi, or highly populated cells of yeast forms within the non-bound stromal lamellae. This aggressive growth has no observable chemotactic secretions, or antigenic behaviour, leading to a noticeable delaying of the beneficial host immune response, and mechanisms, that may inhibit the fungal growth naturally (Cristol *et al.*, 1996).

Mycotic keratitis was observed to record highly increasing rates in the last 3 decades, and possessed a noticeable world wide distribution with higher incidence in regions of warm humid climate. Dandona *et al.* (1997) stated that fungal infections were higher in tropical, and subtropical areas, and mycotic keratitis acted as a major problem in most developing countries, and mainly responsible for corneal morbidity. The same is mostly similar to the statement of Garg and Rao (1999), who recorded that fungal infections were responsible for 50% of corneal scarring cases in developing world, which was a direct cause of blindness.

In Paraguay, 136 cases of mycotic keratitis were recorded out of 661 cases of microbial corneal ulcers in a 3-year study (Laspina *et al.*, 2004). That was proved by the statement of Godoy *et al.* (2004) in Brazil, reporting an observable spread of mycotic

keratitis as 39 cases of mycotic keratitis during 1-year survey. In Egypt, mycotic keratitis possessed a highly increased incidence. About 70 cases of mycotic corneal ulcers were recorded in Upper Egypt during 28 months study (Moharram *et al.*, 1999). These findings were confirmed by similar records of 2-years study in Delta region, illustrating 73 cases of fungal corneal ulcers in a detailed review (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2004).

Many wide spread fungi with distinct air-borne spore dissemination may act as the major fungal population in several corneal ulcer surveys; which could be confirmed by the isolation of different *Aspergillus* species from about 40% of corneal ulcer cases in north India (Chander and Sharma, 2004). In the meantime, in a 3-years survey in south India, different *Fusarium* species were isolated from 47 cases out of 318 cases of mycotic keratitis (Gopinathan *et al.*, 2002). In addition, many *Penicillium* species were commonly isolated from 37% of mycotic keratitis cases in China (Lu and Wang, 2001).

Two-year study in China revealed that 33% of mycotic keratitis cases were contact lens users (Wu *et al.*, 2004). Similar report was stated by Sharma *et al.* (2003) recording that about 36% of the studied mycotic keratitis cases were elementary caused by the soft contact lenses wear. Immunosuppression in ocular tissues by prolonged antibiotic, and corticosteroid was recorded as an observable history for about 26% of mycotic keratitis cases diagnosed after ocular surgery (Djalilian *et al.*, 2001). In Paraguay, Laspina *et al.* (2004) stated that fungal infections of cornea were common in vegetative trauma for patients with agricultural occupations.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

One-year survey was carried out during the period from 1/1/2008 to 31/12/2008. Collected samples were achieved at regular once a week visits to the outpatient clinic, and inpatient department of ophthalmology hospital, Tanta University, Egypt. Samples were collected from patients that were clinically diagnosed to have different types of corneal ulcers. Different types of corneal ulcers were clinically diagnosed, and distinguished from each other on the basis of some clinical criteria (Sandhu and Rattan, 1981; Pavan-Langstone, 1994).

All patient eyes were clinically investigated, and proved to have diagnosed infectious ulcers; for which microbial infections were photographed by instant camera (Sony cybershot-DCR-480, Japan) at magnification of 10X. For each patient, much information were collected to analyze their circumstancing conditions such as: age, gender, family crowding, residence (type of house, water source, and sewage disposal),

climate, patient occupation, patient health history (infected eye, site of infection, type of ocular trauma, corticosteroid therapy, antimicrobial therapy, and other chronic systemic disease history). Statistical analysis was carried out for all row data collected from patients of corneal ulcers during one-year survey through one way ANOVA test, Duncan's multiple range test, and cluster analysis, using SPSS program version 10. This analysis evaluates the significance of the studied risk factors, affecting the incidence of human keratitis. Additional analysis was adopted for patients of confirmed mycotic ulcers, so cluster analysis was performed for different categories of effective predisposing factors, and isolated fungi to group them according to their related spreading factors, using Systat program (Systat Software, San Jose, CA, USA).

All samples were collected by flamed "Kummra" platinum spatula (Alcon-Couvreur, Belgium) for hard tissues or by Ethylene gas-sterilized single use cotton swab (BioMed, China) for soft ulcers to avoid perforation. For sensitive patients with increased pain and hyper-reaction, anesthesia was used as a topical eye drop (Boxinate, Alex. Pharma, Egypt), this was tested for non antimicrobial activity. Aseptic conditions of sampling were considered by: firstly avoiding conjunctiva, and eye lids during corneal scraping; secondly Betadine (Nile Pharma, Cairo, Egypt.) was applied as a gentle washing around infected eyes; also samples were isolated in a closed controlled room in the hospital laboratory. Then C-streaks were made on culture plates to distinguish microbial growth coming from corneal scraping, and other plate contaminants (Margo and Brinser, 1987). Each sample was cultured on 3 sterile Petri dishes with sterile Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) medium, that was composing of 30 g dextrose, 10 g peptone, and 20 g agar per 1 L of distilled water. Chloramphenicol was added to SDA with concentration of 0.05% to avoid bacterial growth for more specific and selective isolation of fungi. All plates were incubated at 27°C for 4 to 21 days. Fungal colonies were sub cultured for purification, and identification on the same medium under the same incubation conditions.

All purified fungal plates were photographed by instant camera (Sony Cybershot - DCR - 480E, Japan); then morphologically, and microscopically examined to be identified according to Raper and Thom (1949), Gilman (1959), Raper and Fennel (1965), Raper *et al.* (1968), Booth (1971), Ellis (1971), and Moubasher (1993).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Seasonal distribution was significantly effective as a predisposing factor for all

studied types of human corneal ulcers. Table 1 illustrates the variation of different types of human corneal ulcers during the different seasons of the year 2008. Summer season recorded the highest incidence for the total of all ulcers (216 cases = 36.3% out of total ulcer cases), and also for each type of ulcer, followed by spring season (189 cases = 31.8% out of total ulcer cases). On the other hand, winter season recorded the lowest incidence for the total of all ulcers (79 cases = 13.3% out of total ulcer cases), and also for each type of ulcers. Traumatic ulcers were highly represented in summer, and spring seasons (106 cases for each). Viral and bacterial ulcer records were highest in summer season (45 and 40 cases, respectively). Traumatic, viral, and bacterial ulcers possessed the least presentation in winter season (40, 16, and 20 cases, respectively) as shown in table 1. More detailed studies were adopted for mycotic ulcers. Table 1 illustrates that mycotic ulcers possessed their highest rate during the year of survey in summer season (25 cases = 50% out of total mycotic ulcers), followed by spring season (17 cases = 34% out of total mycotic ulcers), autumn (5 cases = 10% out of total mycotic ulcers), and the lowest incidence of mycotic infections was recorded in winter season (only 3 cases = 6% out of total mycotic ulcers).

Table 1. Seasonal variations of different types of human corneal ulcers during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Season	Traumatic ulcer	Viral ulcer	Bacterial ulcer	Mycotic ulcers		Total cases	
				No. of cases	% out of mycotic ulcers	No. of cases	% out of total ulcers
Winter (1-3/2008)	40 ^b	16 ^c	20 ^c	3 ^c	6	79 ^b	13.3
Spring (4-6/2008)	106 ^a	31 ^b	35 ^b	17 ^c	34	189 ^a	31.8
Summer (7-9/2008)	106 ^a	45 ^b	40 ^b	25 ^b	50	216 ^a	36.3
Autumn (10-12/2008)	61 ^b	21 ^c	24 ^c	5 ^c	10	111 ^b	18.6
Total cases	313 ^a	113 ^b	119 ^b	50 ^c	100	595	100
F. value	7071.62 [*]	7052.32 [*]	7015.45 [*]	7056.56 [*]		7045.82 [*]	
P. value			0.0001				

Values with different letters are significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

* = Values have highly significant variations according to ANOVA test.

These records were supported by the statement of Alkatan *et al.* (2012) in Saudi Arabia, as they recorded mycotic keratitis in about 7.9% of all diagnosed ulcers in their 4-year survey. On the other hand, Fata *et al.* (2010) referred the main cause of corneal ulcers in Iran to the traumatic origin, more than the microbial infections of different types. Similar findings were recorded by Chen and Lee (2011) for another study on mycotic keratitis; they counted mycotic infections in

about 6% of total studied cases of corneal ulcers; the highest rate was recorded for traumatic origin. Leck *et al.* (2002) collected about 42% among the studied mycotic keratitis cases in their survey during the summer season in south India. In another local study in Upper Egypt, Moharram *et al.* (1999) reported that the higher incidence of mycotic ulcers was documented in summer season (38% of total studied cases). In the mean time, in Lower Egypt, El-Badry (2006) recorded the highest rates of mycotic keratitis during summer, and spring seasons (31 and 24 cases, respectively, out of total 73 cases) in a 2-year survey.

Table 2 reveals that mycotic ulcers were observed to be more common among patients aged more than 40 years old (23 cases = 46% out of total mycotic ulcers), and lowered gradually among youth and children to be only 12 cases (= 24% out of total mycotic ulcers) for patients of less than 20 years old. From table 2 it is obviously noticeable that mycotic keratitis was more common among males (32 cases = 64% out of total mycotic ulcers) more than females (18 cases = 36% out of total mycotic ulcers) for all studied cases. Another important risk factor affecting the spread of mycotic keratitis was the family crowding index. It was observed that mycotic ulcers recorded higher rates in families of crowding index ≥ 4 persons (28 cases = 56% out of total mycotic ulcers), than less populated families as illustrated in table 2.

Table 2. Personal data of patients, affecting distribution of human mycotic keratitis during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Parameter	Category	No. of cases	Percentage out of total cases
Age	< 20 years	12	24
	20 – 40 years	15	30
	> 40 years	23	46
	Total	50	100
Gender	Male	32	64
	Female	18	36
Family crowding index	Total	50	100
	< 4	22	44
	≥ 4	28	56

These findings were in agreement with the results stated by Alkatan *et al.* (2012), who recorded about 40% of their studied cases within the age ranged between 50-60 years of male patients. Rajmane *et al.* (2011) reported about 48% of mycotic keratitis cases in male patients, aged ≥ 45 years, and lived with families ≥ 5 members.

From table 3, it is evident that social hygiene parameters had a great effect on the spreading of infectious human mycotic corneal ulcers. Patients holding rural houses possessed higher incidence of mycotic ulcers (31 cases = 62% out of total mycotic ulcers), more than those in urban houses (19 cases =

38% out of total mycotic ulcers). This factor could be elucidated by the spread of mycotic ulcers among patients depending on outdoor water pumps (28 cases = 56% out of total mycotic ulcers), and conservancy sewage disposal (26 cases = 52% out of total mycotic ulcers). These patients were recorded to be more than those depending on indoor water pipes (22 cases = 44% out of total mycotic ulcers), and sewage disposal by closed pipe networks (24 cases = 48% out of total mycotic ulcers) as seen in table 3.

Table 3. Residential conditions of patients, affecting distribution of human mycotic keratitis during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Parameter	Category	No. of cases	Percentage out of total cases
Type of house	Rural	31	62
	Urban	19	38
	Total	50	100
Water source	Indoor pipes	22	44
	Outdoor pumps	28	56
	Total	50	100
Sewage disposal	Closed pipe networks	24	48
	Conservancy	26	52
	Total	50	100

For this concept, Keay *et al.* (2011) reported about 46% of mycotic keratitis cases among the country side inhabitants, with rural houses during a 6-year study. Also, Baharathi *et al.* (2003) reported a detailed study in India on mycotic keratitis, in which about 56% of cases among rural inhabitants, recorded to use with outdoor water pumps, and conservancy sewage disposal. Jastaneiah *et al.* (2011) reported 124 cases of mycotic keratitis among rural residents in Sudan, during summer seasons of a 5-year survey.

Table 4 represent whether the infected eyes, the right or the left; and the site of corneal infections, central or peripheral, for the studied mycotic ulcer patients. Examination of the infected eye showed higher incidence of mycotic infection in right eyes (34 cases = 68% out of total mycotic ulcers), than left eyes (16 cases = 32% out of total mycotic ulcers). Also mycotic infection recorded higher rate in central cornea (31 cases = 62% out of total mycotic ulcers) as a major sign for fungal growth within corneal tissues, than peripheral non specific infections (19 cases = 38% out of total mycotic ulcers).

Table 4. Orientation of the infected eyes of mycotic keratitis patients, and site of corneal lesion during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Parameter	Category	No. of cases	Percentage out of total cases
Infected eye	Right	34	68
	Left	16	32
	Total	50	100
Site of corneal lesion	Central	31	62
	Peripheral	19	38
	Total	50	100

These findings were in agreement with the statement of Castón-Osorio *et al.* (2008), who recorded about 58% of represented mycotic keratitis in right eyes. The same findings was stated in another study, recording more than 70% of studied fungal infections in right eyes, with central corneal lesions (Moorthy *et al.*, 2012).

Medical history revealed that prolonged administration of antibiotics, corticosteroid drugs, and chronic diseases treatment such as diabetes, and hypertension could greatly affect the immune system of patients, causing immuno-compromised corneal surface, resulting in more susceptibility for fungal invasion. High rate of mycotic ulcers was recorded for previously antibiotic-treated patients (25 cases = 50% out of total mycotic ulcers), followed by corticosteroid-treated patients (19 cases = 38% out of total mycotic ulcers) as illustrated in table 5. Also high rate of mycotic infection of cornea was recorded for chronic diabetes patients (23 cases = 46% out of total mycotic ulcers), then hypertension patients (21 cases = 42% out of total mycotic ulcers).

Table 5. Effect of patient medical history on the distribution of human mycotic keratitis during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Parameter	Category	No. of cases	Percentage out of total cases
Chemotherapy	Antibiotic	25	50
	Steroid	19	38
	None	6	12
	Total	50	100
Chronic systemic disease	Diabetes	23	46
	Hypertension	21	42
	None	6	12
Total	50	100	

None = incomplete stated data

These results were supported by the findings of Alkatan *et al.* (2012), who reported that about 49% of studied mycotic keratitis cases were closely related to immune suppression by antibiotic and corticosteroid treatment. These findings could be also reported by Chen and Lee (2011), who stated that 60% of mycotic keratitis cases were related to antibiotic treatment, and absence of normal microflora of the patient eye surface.

Patients' occupational career could also affect the type of trauma, its incidence, and microorganisms that may come intact with their cornea. Table 6 represents high incidence of mycotic ulcers among students (15 cases = 30% out of total mycotic ulcers), who were intact more to dusty contaminations, and contaminated commercial coloured contact lenses. Farmers come in the second order with a record of 12 cases (= 24% out of total mycotic ulcers) due to dealing with plant crops, and animal wastes contaminated with fungal spores. Housewives

possessed moderate mycotic ulcer incidence (10 cases = 20% out of total mycotic ulcers) due to dealing with indoor dust contaminants; also handy professionals with metallic trauma possessed moderate incidence of mycotic ulcers (8 cases = 16% out of total mycotic ulcers). On the other hand, indoor employees recorded the lowest incidence of mycotic ulcers (5 cases = 10% out of total mycotic ulcers) due to their exposure to less contaminated habitat.

Table 6. Occupational career of patients, affecting distribution of human mycotic keratitis during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Category	No. of cases	Percentage out of total cases
Farmers	1	24
Housewives	10	20
Handy professionals	8	16
Indoor employees	5	10
Students	15	30
Total	50	100

Al-Otaibi (2012) reported higher incidence of mycotic keratitis among female students of contact lens users (43% of total studied cases). While Keay *et al.* (2011) documented severe and rapid spread of mycotic keratitis among USA students, as a progressive epidemic phenomenon; they recorded this relationship for 268 cases out of 733 studied cases in a 6-year survey.

In the present study, table 7 reveals that mycotic infection acted as a secondary infection for injured cornea with different types of trauma, and different origins of contamination with opportunistic fungal spores. During the year of the present survey, contact lens usage recorded the highest rate of fungal contamination, and human mycotic corneal infections (21 cases = 42% out of total mycotic ulcers) with very dangerous, and complicated ulcers. Organic trauma is a fungal spore-contaminated wound, caused by an organic matter of plant, or animal origin, recording 14 cases (= 28% out of total mycotic ulcers) as a common predisposing factor for human mycotic keratitis. In the meantime, ocular surgery, and metallic trauma possessed the lowest rates in affecting the spread of mycotic ulcers (5 cases, and 4 cases = 10%, and 8% out of total mycotic ulcers, respectively).

Table 7. Origin of trauma for the represented human mycotic keratitis patients during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Category	No. of cases	Percentage out of total cases
Metallic trauma	4	8
Organic trauma	14	28
Ocular surgery	5	10
Contact lens usage	21	42
None observed cause	6	12
Total	50	100

Many reviews were found to report these findings. Keay *et al.* (2011) referred the increased incidence of mycotic keratitis to a main reason, namely usage of commercial contact lenses. In the mean time, Jastaneiah *et al.* (2011) elucidated a strong relationship between rapid increasing in mycotic keratitis rates, and non-organized contact lenses usage. Moreover, another recent study was carried out by Moorthy *et al.* (2012), who reported that about 30% of studied mycotic keratitis cases were contact lens users, and 28% of them were organic object dealers.

In conclusion, the most severe risk factors affecting the spread of mycotic keratitis among patients in the present survey were represented in figure 1. It was observed that mycotic keratitis occurred in patients aged > 40 years (23 cases = 46% out of total cases), and more spread among male patients (32 cases = 64% out of total cases). Patients with family crowding index ≥ 4 were more susceptible to mycotic keratitis (28 cases = 56% out of total cases). Patients living in rural houses (31 cases = 62% out of total cases), with outdoor water pumps (28 cases = 56% out of total cases), and sewage disposal by conservancy (26 cases = 52% out of total cases) possessed more frequent fungal infections than other residential habitats. Right eyes (34 cases = 68% out of total cases) with central corneal infections (31 cases = 62% out of total cases) were observed to be more susceptible to fungal infections, than left eyes, and peripheral corneal lesions. On the other hand, previous antibiotic treatment (25 cases = 50% out of total cases), and chronic diabetes patients (23 cases = 46% out of total cases) possessed higher frequency of fungal keratitis. Also fungal corneal ulcers were mostly recorded among students (15 cases = 30% out of total cases), and originated as a secondary infection accompanying the usage of contact lenses (21 cases = 42% out of total cases), which were the most susceptible categories. This data summarization should evaluate the hazard role of different patient circumstances in facilitating his exposure to corneal fungal infection. It could be a new trend of patients' awareness for better hygienic behaviours that help in avoiding infection, and limitation of fungal spread from patients to healthy people. Cluster analysis was carried out, and represented graphically in figure 2 to elucidate the relationship among different effective predisposing factors; that explain the related patient's circumstances, and their role in the increased distribution of mycotic keratitis. Commonly, the analyzed patient data showed related patient circumstances, which were summarized in very closely related groups. The first group was gathered in male farmers, aged ≥ 40 years, inhabiting rural houses with families ≥ 4 members, with dependence on outdoor water sources, and

conservancy sewage disposal; these were mostly suffering from organic trauma of plant or animal origin together. The second group included patients suffering from contaminated surgical injuries, prolonged antibiotic therapy, and corticosteroid treatment for immunocompromised patients. On the other

hand, the third group was related to handy professionals, housewives, and indoor employees with metallic trauma, right eye infections, and chronic diabetes. In the mean time, the fourth group was closely gathered in female students with the non organized contact lens usage.

Fig. 1. Evaluation of the most frequent predisposing factors, increasing the incidence of mycotic keratitis during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Fig. 2. Cluster analysis for the most frequent predisposing factors, increasing the incidence of mycotic keratitis during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Table 8. Fungi isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008)

Isolated fungal species	No. of isolate cases	Percentage out of total mycotic ulcer cases	Time for first growth appearance on culture plates (days)
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> var. <i>flavus</i> (Link)	19	38	4
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (Tiegh)	12	24	4
<i>Penicillium lanosum</i> (Westling)	9	18	9
<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> var. <i>moniliforme</i>	6	12	9
<i>Mucor fuscus</i> (Bainier)	2	4	4
<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i> (Penz)	2	4	14

Table 8 illustrates the fungal species isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers during the year of survey (2008). The data revealed that *Aspergillus flavus* was the most common isolate (19 cases = 38% out of total mycotic ulcers) among all identified isolates, followed by *Aspergillus niger* (12 cases = 24% out of total mycotic ulcers), then *Penicillium lanosum* (9 cases = 18% out of total mycotic ulcers). *Fusarium moniliforme* was isolated from 6 cases (= 12% out of total mycotic ulcers), while two other fungal species were rarely represented among the studied ulcers, namely *Mucor fuscus*, and *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* (only 2 cases for each isolate).

The relationship between different causative agents of mycotic keratitis, and their different predisposing factors were subjected to cluster analysis study, which was represented graphically in figure 3. The resultant dendrogram summarized all represented fungal species in 3 groups at different levels of similarity (75%, 50%, and 25%). It was obviously noticeable that *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus niger* were gathered in the first group at 75% similarity level; these fungal species are common in the air, beside both were originated from organic matter contamination, as clinically reported in the patients records at the hospital, as these fungal species spread among patients exposing to plant crops, and animal wastes contaminated

with fungal spores. The second group was gathered at the 50% similarity level, including *Penicillium lanosum*, and *Fusarium moniliforme*, which are of air-borne origin, and commonly appeared in ulcers of contact lens users, housewives, students, and indoor employees of dust contamination, as clinically reported in the hospital. The third group was separated at the 25% similarity level, including the rarely isolated *Mucor fuscus*, and *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, which were observed to be common in cases of metallic trauma, and appeared in ulcers of some handy professionals, as clinically reported.

Many recent studies confirmed the spread of certain fungal species as causative agents for mycotic keratitis. Alkatan *et al.* (2012) recorded 28% of studied mycotic ulcers to be caused by different *Aspergillus* species, followed by 25% of cases for different *Fusarium* species. On the other hand, Chen and Lee (2011) recorded different *Penicillium* species in about 22% of studied cases of mycotic keratitis. Another study recorded different *Fusarium* isolates in 85 cases of mycotic keratitis by Rajmane *et al.* (2011). In a detailed study on 148 cases of fungal corneal ulcers *Aspergillus* isolates were identified in 36 cases, followed by *Fusarium* in 42 cases with more frequent rates during summer, and spring seasons for both (Vemuganti *et al.*, 2002).

Figure 4 A-1 represents a severe endophthalmitis, accompanying *Aspergillus flavus* corneal infection; which is a deep growth of the fungus with increased thickness of infected lesion due to interference of fungal hyphae with stromal lamellae, causing severe inflammations of all internal eye tissues, taking in consideration the secretion of aflatoxins, and enzymes, which are certainly effective in the disease incidence. Figure 4 B-1) illustrates a noticeable corneal perforation, accompanying *Aspergillus niger* corneal infection; which is a dissolution of definite lesions on corneal epithelium, bearing a pored surface of cornea,

caused by fungal growth within corneal tissues, and secretion of the fungal hydrolytic enzymes (collagenase, proteases, and phospholipase). Photos (Fig. 4 A-2 & B-2) illustrate the culture colonies of *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus niger*, respectively, isolated from human mycotic ulcers, which were situated in the first cluster of isolated fungal species. Photos (Fig. 4 A-3 & B-3) represent each of the causative organisms in the first group of 75% similarity, as examined by light microscope.

Fig. 4. Human mycotic corneal ulcers caused by *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus niger* (A-1, and B-1); colony of each (A-2, and B-2); and light microscope illustrations (A-3, and B-3), respectively.

Figure 5 A-1 shows the appearance of *Penicillium lanosum* corneal infection with distinct hypopyon, which is an accumulative immunoglobulin precipitate surrounding the lesion of fungal growth within the corneal tissues as an immune response of human against the released fungal antigens around the site of infection. The whitish appearance and hardened precipitation is

irreversible, causing complete impairing of vision. Figure 5 B-1 illustrates a severe melting of cornea, accompanying *Fusarium moniliforme* corneal infection; as collagenase activity of the fungus leads hydrolysis of collagen molecules, that could maintain the corneal layers in a compact form, and causes the loosening of corneal stromal lamellae, softening, and thinning of corneal layers. Figure 5 A-2 & B-2 illustrate the culture colonies of the causative agents of the examined human mycotic ulcers situated in the second group of 50% similarity of isolated fungal species, namely *Penicillium lanosum*, and *Fusarium moniliforme*, respectively. Figure 5 A-3 & B-3 represents each of the causative organisms in the second group as examined by light microscope.

Fig. 5. Human mycotic corneal ulcers caused by *Penicillium lanosum*, and *Fusarium moniliforme* (A-1, and B-1); colony of each (A-2, and B-2); and light microscope illustrations (A-3, and B-3), respectively.

Figure 6 A-1 represents a corneal scar, accompanying *Mucor fuscus* corneal infection; as the dense fungal growth, and secretion of

fungal toxins caused toxification of corneal cells, and permanent fibrosis of killed corneal cells, mixed with fungal elements in a compact non transparent form, leading to an irreversible, hardened, whitish, raised, central lesion within the infected cornea. Figure 6 B-1 shows a distinct corneal facet, accompanying *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* corneal infection; as compact fungal growth causing a raised, hardened tumor formed of toxified corneal cells, within the corneal tissues in the range of the infected lesion. Figure 6 A-2 & B-2 illustrate the culture colonies of the causative agents of the examined human mycotic ulcers situated in the third group of 25% similarity of isolated fungal species in the present survey, which were identified as *Mucor fuscus*, and *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, respectively. Figure 6 A-3 & B-3 represents each of the causative organisms in the first cluster as examined by light microscope.

Fig. 6. Human mycotic corneal ulcers caused by *Mucor fuscus*, and *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* (A-1, and B-1); colony of each (A-2, and B-2); and light microscope illustrations (A-3, and B-3), respectively.

Complications of mycotic keratitis were commonly recorded in many reviews. Chen *et al.* (2004) reported a secondary endophthalmitis, accompanying post keratoplasty fungal infection. Also, corneal perforation was recorded as a major complication associated with fungal infections after corneal transplantation (Wakimasu *et al.*, 2004). Endophthalmitis was observed as a

feared complication of trauma, with significant visual loss, accompanying post surgical contaminations, and fungal infections with delayed treatment; that was reported to possess increasing rates in relation to the wide spectrum of involved microorganisms as a main reason of infectious endophthalmitis (Safneck, 2012).

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وبائية القرحة الفطرية لقرنية الإنسان بمستشفى الرمد بجامعة طنطا

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سببا قرحة مركزية فى العين اليمنى. ومن جهة أخرى، تم عزل المسببات الفطرية لقرحة القرنية من 50 حالة بين 595 حالة من أنواع القرحة المختلفة.

المحكمون:

قسم النبات، علوم بنها
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تهدف الدراسة الحالية إلى تقييم انتشار القرحة الفطرية لقرنية الإنسان على أساس العوامل المسببة لها. وقد وجد أن مستخدمى العدسات اللاصقة والمزارعين هم الأكثر عرضه للقرحة الفطرية للقرنية؛ كما أن الرجال ذوى المناعة المنخفضة فوق سن الأربعين وقاطنى المنازل الريفية هم الأعلى تردداً على هذه الإصابة فى فصلى الربيع والصيف. كما وجد أن فطرى الأسيبيرجلاس فلافاس والأسيبيرجلاس نايجر هما الأكثر شيوعاً بين الحالات محل الدراسة، حيث